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Marine Protected Areas Odyssey

Virsko-More archipelago (Croatia)

September 2024

Marine Protected Areas Odyssey – Report of the 2024 mission in the Virsko-More archipelago (Croatia)

May 2025

FOREWORD

Context, fundings and partner: This study is part of the "MPA Odyssey in the Mediterranean Sea" program, developed by WWF-France and realised in partnership with Septentrion Environnement (SE). This report presents the actions undertaken and the results of the field mission of fall 2024, carried out in the Virsko-More archipelago. The partners associated with this mission are the WWF Adriatic. The project is co-funded thanks to the financial support of the Pew Bertarelli Ocean Legacy.

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1. Introduction

This study is part of the Marine Protected Areas Odyssey program, directed by WWF-France, in the Mediterranean. The MPA Odyssey is a multi-year scientific field expedition, aiming at strengthening the impact of MMI (Mediterranean Marine Initiative) advocacy so that 30% of the Mediterranean is protected and in the process of recovery while 3% is under a strong protection status.

This report outlines research activities as well as associated results of the field mission carried out within the Virsko more archipelago (northwest of Croatia) from September 23rd to October 5th, 2024, by WWF-France and Septentrion Environnement, with the assistance of WWF Adriatic. The main objective of this mission was to collect data through visual censuses carried out underwater aimed at describing and analysing the state of the fish assemblages (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 1985) within the studied area (Fig. 1) in order to (1) identify sites that are likely to be included into protected zones in the future; (2) To place these data in perspective with those from other Mediterranean areas.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study Area

The team who carried out the Virsko More mission was made up of 6 scientific divers who carried out the underwater visual census, a mission leader, a scientific supervisor and 4 crew members (**Tab. 1**).

Table 1. The scientific and technical team, conducting the field expedition within the Virsko More archipelago.

Scientific team	Role within the expedition	Organization
Dr. Denis ODY	Mission leader/Surface safety/ Scientific diver	WWF France
Tristan ESTAQUE	Scientific supervision	Septentrion Environnement
Lucie NUNEZ	Scientific diver	Septentrion Environnement
Gaëlle TABET	Scientific diver	Septentrion Environnement
Anouck ODY	Scientific diver	Septentrion Environnement
Olivier Bianchimani	Scientific diver	Septentrion Environnement
Sébastien Personnic	Scientific diver	Septentrion Environnement
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Louis du Petit Thouars	Sailor	WWF France
Marion George	Sailor	WWF France
Isabelle de la Giraudière	Sailor	WWF France

45 sites spread over the Virsko More archipelago were sampled (Fig. 1). Sites were selected based on available data regarding the description of biotopes and biocenoses along the coastline. The selected sites had to present habitats with the following characteristics: subtidal rocky reefs that can be partially covered (< 50%) with *P. oceanica* meadows, located between 5 and 12 m deep. This habitat was targeted as it is a representative case study to quantify the response of fish assemblages to the level of protection (Garcia-Rubies and Zabala, 1990). However, some variations in habitat characteristics remained, sometimes showing shallower rocky bottoms (3–5 m), and a minimum depth of 1 meter at one site (18). Sites and their characteristics are listed in Appendix A1 and in the result full database (available upon request).

Figure 1. Studied zones and sites within the Virsko More archipelago. Sites are represented by a red dot and their number. Sites are categorized into 4 zones, including the western (green), the central (blue), the eastern (orange) and the northern (yellow) part of the archipelago.

There are no existing MPAs in the Virsko More, but some areas are included in the Natura 2000 framework, which does not impose any regulations on professional or recreational fishing in these designated areas. As a result, given the absence of specific fishing regulations, the sites were grouped into four zones based on their geographical proximity and similarities in geomorphological characteristics. The sites on the west coast of the different islands forming the archipelago have been gathered into the “West” zone, sites near Olib and Silba islands have been gathered into “North” zone, while the eastern and central sites have been respectively gathered into the “East” and “Center” zones (Fig. 1).

2.2 Sampling method : Underwater Visual Census

The underwater visual census (UVC) method was used to quantify the diversity, abundance, as well as the individual size of fish species. A sampling unit consisting of 25 m long by 5 m wide transects was applied. In each sampling unit, the abundance of each fish species was counted, or estimated for large groups, and their individual size estimated in increments of 2 cm (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008, 1985). A single pass per transect was carried out, focusing on necto-benthic species (sparids, wrasses, serranids, etc.) (Harmelin, 1987) which are the most sensitive to the level of protection and also display an economic importance for local communities (Garcia-Rubies and Zabala, 1990). Cryptic species were not considered.

For each site, 6 transects were conducted following a stratified random sampling design (summing up to 273 transects in total, over the 45 sites), targeting the habitat described above.

2.3 Data analysis

3.3.1. Fish assemblage descriptors

Descriptive variables of fish assemblages were extracted from the raw collected data (specific richness, abundance, size) and included species occurrence (proportion of transects where a species was present), species overall dominance (proportion of individuals of a given species out of the number counted for all species combined), total biomass and relative biomass by species (population composition), as well as abundance by size classes for certain species. Biomass was calculated from the abundance and size of individuals per species using commonly used size-biomass conversion factors for fishes dwelling in the infralittoral rocky reef biocenosis (Thibaut et al., 2017).

After examining the occurrence of species, the gregarious species (*C. chromis*, *Spicara* spp., *B. boops* and *Atherina* spp.), which were very abundant on the majority of transects, were subsequently excluded from the data to prevent masking the signal of less abundant species of performed analysis. Among observed species (Appendix A2), Mediterranean species commonly targeted by fishing were also examined more closely.

A standard list of commercially targeted species in the Mediterranean sea, including (Appendix A3), was used.

The **explanatory variables** of the sampling design were the zone (4 modalities: North, Center, East, West) and the site (45 modalities) (see Fig. 1). Differences in abundance and biomass among zones were tested statistically. Since the data does not have a normal distribution and the homogeneity of variances is not respected, a Kruskal-Wallis test (non-parametric test similar to Anova) was performed. The pairwise differences among the different modalities of the “Zone” factor were then tested using a post-hoc Dunn's test for multiple comparisons, adapted to the Kruskal-Wallis test.

We then compared our data from the Virsko More archipelago within the context of other areas in the Mediterranean, using data from BIOMEX project and the MPA Odyssey project, by comparing mean **biomass, mean abundance and mean richness** across all sites (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008).

All figures and descriptive and inferential statistics were produced with R Studio software version 2024.12.0+467. .

3.3.2. Scenarios of stronger protection

Based on the MPA's Odyssey program results and alongside teleost assemblages results obtained within the Virsko-More Archipelago, a management scenario was proposed, involving the creation of No-Take Zones (NTZ) and Professional Fishing Reserved Areas (PFRAs) (see Fig. 18 in the discussion), where recreational fishing would be prohibited. Fish “Production” that would be expected for this scenario was then compared to that obtained in the current state of the area, for the same superficies.

For a given zone, with a mean *in situ* biomass of fish, the “Production” is what is expected to be produced and exported annually per unit of surface (ha), through natural growth and reproduction of these fish individuals. The Production is directly and positively correlated to the “*in situ* Biomass”. Previous reported studies from the BIOMEX program (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) demonstrated that the “Production/*in situ* Biomass” ratio was between 0.315 and 0.366 on average for sites located inside or outside no-take zones of 6 mediterranean model MPAs, respectively. This ratio [Production]/[*in situ* Biomass] depends also on the proportion of the different categories of fish in the assemblage. Knowing the *in-situ* biomass of a given zone, and using these ratios, it is consequently possible to evaluate the production expected from this given zone under various scenarios. The difference of production between a scenario where the zone becomes a NTZ or remains in the current not-protected situation can be considered as the “revenues of a capital” and also as what would be available for fishing around the NTZ.

The potential “*in situ* biomass” of the new NTZs in the present scenario have been calculated with the *in situ* biomass observed in this study multiplied by the average ratio of [biomass inside]/[outside NTZs] known from 24 mediterranean MPAs (Giakoumi et al., 2017). The value of this ratio is x2.3 and should be considered as rather conservative

since higher values were obtained in the framework of the BIOMEX program (x5.6 in average and up to x9.7; Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) as well as in MPAs Odyssey (*i.e.* Corsica in 2022 - x4.5; Estaque et al., 2023).

The same calculation was performed for designing Professional Fishing Reserved Areas surrounding the NTZs (PFRA). The increase of “*In situ* Biomass” in this Professional Fishing Reserved Areas (PFRA) resulting from prohibiting recreational fishing was investigated. Data from a similar design in Corsica (Estaque et al., 2023), were used in this study, where the *in situ* biomass in the PFRA was 2.7 and 3.7 times higher than in open areas. We used x2 as a conservative estimate.

In summary, we estimated the following:

- The **current production** of a given entire sector before setting up any NTZ or PFRA;
- Its **potential production** increased by the exedentary production resulting from the setting up of the NTZ (*i.e.* production available around the NTZ once protected *versus* production available when not protected), while the rest of the sector remains open to all type of fishing ;
- Its **potential production** increased by the two exedentary productions resulting (a) from the setting up of the **NTZ** and (b) resulting from the setting up of the surrounding **PFRA**.

3. Results

3.1. Sampling and Key Quantitative Properties of Teleostean Communities

3.1.1 Occurrence Frequency, Dominance, and Species Richness

Over the **273 transects sampled over the Virsko-More archipelago**, a total of **40 734 individuals** were counted, belonging to the **41 species** listed in appendix A2. Across all transects, *Diplodus vulgaris* was the most dominant species, representing 23% of total abundance. Moreover, overall species dominance showed that 4 species were responsible for 79% of total abundance across all transects. These species were *Diplodus vulgaris* (23%), *Coris julis* (19%), *Oblada melanura* (19%) and *Symphodus tinca* (18%) (**Fig. 2a**).

Likewise, 5 species showed a frequency of occurrence of at least 70%. Individual of *Coris julis* were recorded in 91% of transects, followed by 4 other species recorded up to 80% of transects: *D.vulgaris* (81%), *S.tinca* (78%), *S.scriba* (74%), and *C.chromis* (73%) (**Fig 2b**).

Figure 2. a) Percentage of overall dominance of species (excluding gregarious species) across all sites and all transects over the Virsko More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The shades of green range from dark to light, with darker green indicating a higher dominance and lighter blue representing lower values. **b)** Percentage of overall occurrence of species (excluding gregarious species) across all sites and all transects over the Virsko More archipelago (same period mentioned above). The shades of green range from dark to light, with darker green indicating a higher occurrence and lighter blue representing lower values.

At the zone level, slight variations were observed in occurrence values. The five most frequently recorded species (*Coris julis*, *Diplodus vulgaris*, *Symphodus tinca*, *Serranus scriba*, and *Chromis chromis*) were more abundant in the eastern, central, and western zones. In the latter zone, a wider range of species also exhibited an occurrence percentage higher than 2% (**Fig. 3**).

Figure 3. Percentage of overall occurrence of species across all sites and all transects per zone, over the Virsko More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The shades of green range from dark to light, with darker green indicating a higher occurrence and lighter blue representing lower values.

The total cumulated species richness, over all zones, was 41 taxa, and ranged from 34 taxa cumulated for the West zone to 26 taxa cumulated for the Center zone. The species richness per transect was on average 7.2 ± 0.2 taxa (considering all sites). Species richness per transect averaged per site varied, from 1 taxa for site 18 (in the Center zone) to 12 taxa for sites 47, 25, and 28 (West archipelago zone) (Fig. 4).

This variation was also observed between sites within each zone, ranging from 1 ± 0.5 taxa per transect for the Center zone to 9 ± 0.8 and from 2 ± 0.6 taxa to 12 ± 0.6 taxa for the West zone (Fig. 4)

Figure 4. Average species richness per transect by site (rounded values are indicated in arabic numbers) across the Virsko-More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The error bars (whiskers) correspond to the standard error, represented here only in positive value (+E.S.) for a better display. The color indicates the zone to which the site belongs.

Finally, the average of species richness per transect per zone varied from 5.9 ± 0.5 taxa per transect for the Center zone to 8.3 ± 0.4 taxa for the West zone (Fig. 5).

Certain species have been rarely observed or only in one zone. Notably, Yellowmouth barracuda (*Sphyraena viridensis*), Common dentex (*Dentext dentex*) and the Small red

scorpionfish (*Scorpaena notata*) were only observed in transects of the western zone, while rabbitfish (*Siganus sp.*), brown meagres (*Sciaena umbra*) and common pandoras (*Pagellus erythrinus*) were only seen in the eastern zone.

Figure 5. Species richness per transect, averaged by zone, all sites combined (rounded values are indicated in arabic numbers) across the Virsko–More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). Error bars correspond to standard error (+/- ES).

3.1.2 Fish assemblage abundance

The mean total abundance of assemblages per zone was 51.9 ± 3.4 ind. 125 m^{-2} (gregarious species excluded) (**Fig. 6**).

The northern zone exhibited a mean total abundance of 63.0 ± 10.3 ind. 125 m^{-2} , which was close to the value observed in the western zone (57.8 ± 4.8 ind. 125 m^{-2}) (**Fig. 6**). The central zone exhibited the lowest mean total abundance of assemblages, with a value of 40.6 ± 4.2 individuals per 125 m^2 . The western and center zones were significantly different in terms of mean total abundance per transect, which was higher in the West zone (Kruskal–Wallis Pairwise comparisons, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 6. Mean total abundance of fish assemblages per zone in the Virsko-More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The whiskers correspond to the standard error (-/+ E.S.). The color indicates the zone. Letters illustrate the significance or non-significance of differences in mean given by statistical tests; two areas with no letters in common differ significantly from each other for the considered response variable.

The mean total abundance of fish (gregarious species excluded) per transect, averaged per site, ranged from 2.3 ± 1.1 ind. 125 m^{-2} at site 39 (North zone) to 137.2 ± 90.4 ind. 125 m^{-2} at site 30 (East zone). This variation was also observed within each zone. Within each zone, the variation of the mean total abundance per transect was, on average, 14 times greater between the sites with the lowest and highest abundance (**Fig.7**). The maximum difference in mean total abundance per transect was observed in the northern zone, where the coefficient of variation between sites reached 53, and varied from 2.3 ± 1.1 ind. 125 m^{-2} at site 39 to 122.5 ± 27.4 ind. 125 m^{-2} at site 37 (**Fig.7**).

Figure 7. Mean total abundance of fish assemblages across all sites (excluding gregarious species) in the Virsko–More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). Fish assemblages per site are categorized per zone, the color indicates the zone. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (\pm E.S.).

We also observed species-specific differences between zones. Wrasses such as *S. roissali*, *S. doderleini*, and *C. melanocercus* were more abundant in the western zone, whereas *S. tinca*, *S. rostratus*, *C. labrosus*, and *S. ocellatus* were more abundant in the eastern zone (Fig. 8). *S. tinca* exhibited high abundance at site 29 (East), reaching 62.8 ± 36.7 ind. 125 m⁻² (Fig. 8).

Finally, numerous species were more abundant in the western zone, including the Yellowmouth barracuda (*S. viridensis*), which was observed exclusively in this zone, as well as the Golden grouper (*E. costae*). Additionally, the Common dentex (*Dentex dentex*), Brown grouper (*E. marginatus*), Mediterranean moray (*M. helena*), and two species of scorpionfish (*S. notata* and *S. porcus*) were also more abundant in this zone (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Mean total abundance of selected taxa, excluding gregarious species, per area in the Virsko–More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The whiskers correspond to the standard error (+/-E.S.) for better display. The color indicates the zone to which the species belongs.

3.1.3 Fish species size (TL)

Overall, for each species of the Teleost assemblage surveyed, the mean lengths (TL: Total Length) of the individuals were fairly similar between the different zones (**Fig. 9**). The fish species targeted by the fishery were not on average larger in any particular zone. Moreover, the mean length of the individuals observed was quite small overall, particularly for individuals of the *Diplodus* genus (see references in discussion section). The average length of individuals was comparable from one zone to another, as for the Sharpnose seabream (*Diplodus puntazzo*) species where the average size varied from 12.7 ± 0.7 cm in the northern zone to 15.0 ± 1.3 cm in the central zone.

Nevertheless, it can be noted that *S. dumerili* individuals were on average smaller in the eastern zone and that *S. salpa* individuals were on average smaller in the northern zone.

Figure 9. Mean total length of selected taxa (TL: Total Length, in cm) , excluding gregarious species, per area in the Virsko–More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The whiskers correspond to the standard error (-E.S.) for better display. The color indicates the zone to which the species belongs.

3.1.4 Fish assemblage biomass

The mean biomass per transect averaged per site (**Fig. 10**) varied from $4.0 \pm 3.1 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ for site 39 (North zone) to $10\ 800.8 \pm 5857.5 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ for site 47 (West zone). The biomass average for all transects combined (gregarious species excluded) was $1\ 559.6 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2} \pm 196.6 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$.

Sites located inside the western zone showed a higher average biomass than the other sites. Only site 47 was characterized by a biomass superior to $10\ 000 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ (as mentioned above). These high biomass values were primarily driven by *Seriola dumerili*, with an averaged biomass observed per site of $2\ 933.7 \pm 1\ 833.7 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$; *Sphyraena viridensis* ($2\ 255.3 \pm 2\ 255.3 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$) and *Diplodus vulgaris* ($2263.9 \pm 1024.7 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$). Finally, sites 25 and 28 (West zone) showed a mean biomass of fish assemblages per transects higher than $2\ 000 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$ (respectively $2509.0 \pm 503.1 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$, $4\ 134.0 \pm 2193.8 \text{ g} \cdot 125 \text{ m}^{-2}$) (**Fig. 10**). At the zone level (**Fig. 11**) the mean total biomass did not vary significantly between zones ($p > 0,05$).

Figure 10. Mean biomass of fish assemblages across all sites during the field campaign in the Virsko-More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The whiskers correspond to the standard error ($- S.E.$).

Figure 11. Mean biomass of fish assemblages per zone in the Virsko-More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The whiskers correspond to the standard error ($+/- E.S.$). The color indicates the zone to which the site belongs.

3.1.5 Case of two emblematic species : *Epinephelus marginatus* and *Sciaena umbra*

Among the targeted grouper species, only one species was seen in 3 zones: *Epinephelus marginatus*, where a maximum of individuals were observed in the western zone, with a total abundance of 4 individuals at site 47 (Fig. 12a), for an average size of 20 cm (Fig.12b). Golden groupers (*Epinephelus costae*) were only observed in the western zone at site 47, while *Brown meagres* (*Sciaena umbra*) were only observed at one site in the eastern zone (Fig.12a).

Figure 12. a) Total abundance of emblematic species including *E. costae*, *E. marginatus* and *S. umbra*, across all sites in the Virsko–More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). Total abundances per site are categorized per zone, the color indicates the zone to which the site belongs. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (- E.S.). **b) The mean total length** (TL; cm) of emblematic

species including *E. costae*, *E. marginatus* and *S. umbra*, across all sites during autumn-2024, in the Virsko-More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The mean total length is categorized per zone, the color indicates the zone to which the site belongs. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (- E.S.).

Biomass of the three emblematic species was overall similar in all zones, with slightly higher values in the eastern and center zones (**Fig. 13**).

Figure 13. The mean biomass of emblematic including *E. marginatus*, *M. rubra* and *S. umbra*, across all sites during autumn-2024 in the Virsko-More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The biomass is categorized per zone, the color indicates the zone to which the site belongs. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (- E.S.).

3.1.6 Species targeted by fishing

For a subset of commercial species (*D. annularis*, *D. puntazzo*, *D. sargus*, *D. vulgaris*, *D. dentex*, *C. julis*, *L. merula*, *L. viridis*, *M. surmuletus*, *O. melanura*, *S. scribea*, *S. salpa*, et *S. aurata*), no zone seemed to stand out in terms of mean specific abundance. The West zone displayed slightly higher mean abundances of *Coris julis* and *Dentex dentex* (only seen in this zone) with respectively 15 ± 1.43 ind. 125 m^{-2} and 0.027 ± 0.019 ind. 125 m^{-2} (**Fig.14a**). *Sparus aurata* showed higher mean abundances in the center zone whereas *Diplodus sargus*, *Diplodus puntazzo* and *Diplodus vulgaris* were more abundant in the eastern zone.

Regarding total length, no significant differences were observed between areas for these species (**Fig. 14b**). However, the mean biomass displayed a taxa-specific pattern, similar to the mean abundance. Individuals of *D. vulgaris* showed a higher mean biomass (**Fig. 14b**) in the western zone, likely due to their slightly larger total length in this zone (**Fig. 15**).

Figure 14. a) Total mean abundance of species targeted by fishing across all sites ; b) The mean biomass of species targeted by fishing across all sites during autumn-2024, in the Virsko–More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The total mean abundance and the mean biomass are categorized per zone, the color indicates the zone to which the site belongs. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (- E.S.).

Figure 15. The mean total length (TL; cm) of species targeted by fishing across all sites during autumn-2024, in the Virsko-More archipelago, Croatia (on September 23rd and October 5th, 2024). The mean total length is categorized per zone, the color indicates the zone to which the site belongs. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (- E.S.).

3.2 Comparisons with others Mediterranean areas

Here in Virsko More, there was no pre-existing protection status that allowed us to compare differences in average biomass and average abundance between sites with strong protection and sites with a lower protection status. However, with the data gathered over the last 16 years through the BIOMEX program and the MPA Odyssey program (BIOMEX program, Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008), we can put our results into perspective, or at least refute or confirm the effects of a lack of strong protection on fish assemblages (Table 2, Fig. 16).

As regards biomass, the Virsko More area (Natura 2000 sites without strong protection) had the lowest mean biomass per unit area of all studied areas of the BIOMEX project and the MPA Odyssey project (Table 1 ; Fig. 16). The mean biomass was similar (but still slightly lower) to other unprotected areas such as those in Cape Corsica, Bonifacio or Lastovo.

As regards abundances, the Virsko More area had the third lowest mean abundance per unit area after the Tagomago unprotected zone (MPA Odyssey project) and the Medes Unprotected zone (BIOMEX project) (Table 2 ; Fig. 16).

Finally, as regards mean species richness, the Virsko–More area displayed the lowest mean number of observed species among all studied areas (ranging from min 7.2 to max 14.1) (Table. 2).

As a conclusion, it is worth noting that fish assemblages we described from the Virsko–More archipelago were among the poorest described within the available Mediterranean dataset. Although such data can not be totally disentangled from local effects of local environmental conditions (geomorphology, water quality, etc.) it is mostly probable that the lack of effective regulations as regards fishing activities and notably that lack of strong protection status zones contribute to this trend.

Figure 16. Descriptors (average biomass and total abundance) of teleost communities in the protected and unprotected areas of the different MPAs studied in the Mediterranean - 2024 data from Virsko More is presented alongside those of western study areas of the BIOMEX program (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) and the MPA Odyssey project (2021–2024). Increasing gradation of protection: Unprotected < Partially or reinforced protection < No-Take Zone (protected).

Table 2. Mean species richness, mean abundance and mean biomass recorded in different Mediterranean MPAs during the BIOMEX (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) and MPA Odyssey (2021–2023) projects. Increasing gradation of protection: Unprotected < Partially protected < No-Take Zone (protected). NB: within the Dilek Peninsula MPA, "Partially protected" status prohibits professional fishing and authorizes recreational fishing. In Lastovo Islands Nature Parks, the No-Take Zones are not yet effective and are only at the project stage. In this study, only the "Unprotected" protection type was observed for Virsko More.

Marine Protected Area	Project	Protection type	Mean species richness	Mean abundance (ind.125 m ⁻²)	Mean Biomass (g.125 m ⁻²)
RN Cerbère-Banyuls	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	11.2	79.2	16 300.0
RN Cerbère-Banyuls	BIOMEX	Unprotected	10.8	70.5	4 000.0
Cabo de Palos	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	12.9	99.0	28 200.0
Cabo de Palos	BIOMEX	Unprotected	9.8	60.1	2 900.0
Cabrera	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	14.1	93.0	13 600.0
Cabrera	BIOMEX	Unprotected	13.9	71.6	2 700.0
Carry le Rouet	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	13.1	99.3	16 300.0
Carry le Rouet	BIOMEX	Unprotected	12.4	64.1	2 400.0
Medes	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	13.8	61.1	17 500.0
Medes	BIOMEX	Unprotected	10.2	31.5	2 700.0
Tabarca	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	12.3	113.6	9 400.0
Tabarca	BIOMEX	Unprotected	13.3	98.3	5 300.0
PNMCCA	MPA Odyssey	No-Take Zone	10.4	58.0	2 771.0
PNMCCA	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	9.7	56.7	1 908.0
Dilek Peninsula	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	9.7	106.7	3 909.0
Dilek Peninsula	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	10.2	100.0	3 720.0
RN Bouches de Bonifacio	MPA Odyssey	No-Take Zone	11.7	106.2	7 185.0
RN Bouches de Bonifacio	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	12.3	118.2	6 654.0
RN Bouches de Bonifacio	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	10.9	85.6	1 829.0
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Integral Reserve / No-Take Zone	12.3	152.8	14 209.0

PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Cantonment / No-Take Zone	11.6	90	30 861.0
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	11.4	121.0	6 694.0
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	10.3	76.5	2 398.0
Tagomago MPA (Ibiza)	MPA Odyssey	Integral Reserve / No-Take Zone	10.1	32.8	4 673.0
Tagomago MPA (Ibiza)	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	11.6	100	6 325.0
Tagomago MPA (Ibiza)	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	9.3	70	2 316.0
Lastovo Islands Nature Park	MPA Odyssey	Future No-Take Zones (but still unprotected)	11.2	74.3	2 646.0
Lastovo Islands Nature Park	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	11.7	77.5	2 296.0
Virsko More archipelago (Natura 2000 sites)	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	7.2	51.84	1 559.6

4. Discussion

4.1. Robustness of the method

The Underwater Visual Census (UVC) method is a well-tested approach that gives reliable results provided that operators are trained and inter-calibrated, a precaution that was taken here (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 1985). More recent methodological variants exist, for example with a transect width that varies according to the species considered (Prato et al., 2017), but the classic version of the UVCs has been preferred here in order to be able to compare the results with the existing literature on previous studies in Mediterranean MPAs (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008).

It should be remembered here that this method is adapted to the inventory of necto-benthic species only. It is therefore not surprising that we hardly observed crypto-benthic species, such as Scorpaenidae, which are rare in our quantitative data.

One of the challenges encountered was sampling a constant habitat. The target habitat (infralittoral rocky reefs at depths between 5 m and 12 m) was not always present, and its geomorphology varied greatly, ranging from rocky slabs covered with macroalgae at shallow depths (averaging 6 m) to rocky drop-offs plunging to greater depths. This variability in habitat characteristics across samples (see Appendix) inevitably introduces some bias, though an acceptable one, which must be taken into account.

4.2. General status of the assemblages

On the whole, the surveys of Teleost fish assemblages that we have carried out showed the presence of the typical species assemblages of the rocky NW Mediterranean infralittoral, but with zones of relatively low species richness and numbers dominated by small size classes compared with other areas of the NW Mediterranean (García-Rubies and Zabala, 1990). This was particularly true in the center of the archipelago, where mean abundance and mean biomass were quite low.

Overall, teleost communities appeared to have a higher species richness and generally higher average abundance and biomass on the less landlocked islands on the periphery of the archipelago, particularly in the northern and western zones.

Three emblematic species *Epinephelus marginatus*, *Epinephelus costae*, and *Sciaena umbra* were seen during the study, but in very low numbers and with small average sizes. Only a single individual of the exotic species *Siganus* sp. was recorded, and no other exotic species was observed. Unlike observations further south in Croatia, particularly in the Lastovo region, thermophilous species were scarce, with few individuals of *Thalassoma pavo* recorded and no observations of *Sparisoma cretense* (Estaque et al., 2024).

4.3 Impact of fishing pressure

Our data showed that the Virsko More area is comparable to other regions without protected status, such as Cape Corsica, Scandola Cantonement, Tabarca, and Dilek Peninsula, where no regulations or effective enforcement mechanisms are in place to mitigate the impact of fishing activities (both recreational and professional) (Fig. 17). This lack of protection likely contributes to the relatively low mean total length observed for all species in Virsko More, with no significant differences between zones (Fig. 11). Similarly, specific abundances remained uniformly low across all zones (Fig. 8), with the overall abundance averaging 51.85 ± 3.4 ind. 125 m^{-2} across all sites.

Following the same pattern, despite the presence of suitable habitats for emblematic species such as *Epinephelus marginatus*, only a few individuals were observed during this study ($n = 13$), mostly of small sizes ranging from 12 cm to 46 cm. These results are consistent with observations from the past 20 years, during which this species has been impacted by recreational fishing, mainly spearfishing in shallow areas like those targeted in our study (Ugarković and Dragičević, 2023).

The Adriatic Sea is characterized by a high fishing effort and a wide diversity of fishing gear, driven by the shared jurisdiction of multiple countries. In terms of fishing zones, its northern region is divided among three nations (Italy, Slovenia, and Croatia) making it one of the most intensively exploited areas in the Mediterranean (Colloca et al., 2017; Dulčić et al., 2007). Our data suggest that the northern Croatian waters, where no specific conservation measures are in place to protect fish stocks, follow the same trend.

4.4 Interesting sites for potential strong protection enforcement

Our results revealed a strong site effect, with mean total biomass and mean total abundance values varying by up to tenfold between sites within the same zone and across zones (**Fig. 7-8**). Despite this inter-zone variability, the western zone stood out due to the presence of particularly rich sites.

This western zone exhibited a higher mean total biomass compared to the other zones (**Fig. 11**), with one notable site, Site 47, distinguished by a particularly high mean total biomass. This was notably due to the observation of a shoal of greater amberjacks (*S. dumerili*), as well as a high abundance of common two-banded seabreams (*D. vulgaris*) and barracudas (*S. viridensis*) (**Fig. 10**). Additionally, Sites 48, 49, 28 and 50 (western zone) also showed strong potential, with an average species richness above the average. Besides, certain sites in the eastern and northern zones exhibited as well, notable values of mean total abundance of fish assemblages. Site 29 and 30 showed significantly higher mean abundances of species of economical interest (such as *Diplodus vulgaris*) compared to other sites, followed by site 41, where the abundance of *Diplodus vulgaris* was also high, along with the presence of *Epinephelus marginatus* individuals. Sites 30 and 41 were characterized by complex underwater seabed (cliffs and reefs). Sites 2, 3, and 4, located near or on rocky drop-offs, were also among the sites that stood out in the data analysis in terms of total mean biomass and abundance, as well as exhibiting a higher mean species richness compared to the entire area (**Fig. 4, 7, 10**). Finally, in the north zone, sites 35-34-31 displayed remarkable values as well.

As it was said earlier, this results confirms a strong site effect in all of the studied zones, this is not surprising given the diversity of micro-habitats we've encountered across the Virsko More archipelago. Thus, our findings align with previous studies in the literature, which show that habitat heterogeneity increases the availability of refuges for fish, ultimately leading to greater diversity in fish communities (García-Charton et al., 2004).

As a conclusion, those sites were selected for inclusion in our recommendations for setting up strong protection zones (see next section).

5. Management recommendations

5.1. General approach

Given the lack of protected zones with effective fishing regulation in the Virsko More area, reinforced protection measures are urgently needed to reverse the observed trend. These measures should include the creation of (1) strong protection zones (= No-Take Zones), (2) along with designated areas open only for small-scale professional fishing (PFRA), both being included within a global Marine Protected Area with an intermediate level of protection, as well as awareness-raising and educational initiatives. All these measures are detailed below.

NTZs should not be taken as “closed” or as “lost fishing ground”, on the contrary, many scientific papers (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) have demonstrated that they produce extra biomass that is exported and become available for fisheries outside. In Carry Le Rouet (France), it has been demonstrated that one 85 ha NTZ produced 106 tonnes of fish biomass each year.

In Virsko More, such NTZs should similarly enhance the available biomass. Besides, surrounding NTZs with zones where only professional fishing is allowed (Professional Fishing Reserved Areas - PFRA) would ensure that the extra biomass produced is directly benefiting the professional fishermen community. For two examples in Corsica (Natural Reserve of Scandola and Bonifacio) in such areas where fishing is only allowed to professional, the biomass present is 4 and 5 times higher than in open areas with no restriction. In Bonifacio, the catch per unit effort (CPUE) has increased by 60% to 80% (80% for species targeted by spearfishing) for fishermen six years after banning recreational fishing from such areas. The Gokova MPA example (Turkey) gives a similar example (Kızılkaya et al., 2025) with landings from small-scale fisheries increasing by +82% in areas surrounding a NTZ, resulting in three fold higher incomes.

Our data suggested that such buffer areas could serve as a crucial intermediary between fully protected areas and unprotected zones. These buffer areas act as a safeguard against excessive pressures outside the fully protected zones, contributing to the overall effectiveness of the conservation strategy ((Claudet et al., 2008; Di Lorenzo et al., 2016). Consequently, such modules coupling NTZ surrounded by areas reserved for professional fishing (PFRA) are **the core of our recommendations for the MPA**. They are the key to combine biodiversity protection, restoration of the halieutic resources, and economical wealth for local fishermen. The next section presents such scenarios.

5.2 Creation of an MPA with No-Take Zones

Our study allowed us to identify some sites richer than average with teleost assemblages in a better state of conservation than other sites and with remarkable habitats. These sites are examples of good candidates for prioritizing the effective implementation of No-Take Zones (NTZs) (see part 4.4). The scientific community has shown that strong protection zones with a surface area of at least 3.6 km² (360 ha) are preferable (Di Franco et al., 2018) to obtain satisfying reserve and spill-over effects. Therefore, in light of the results discussed in Section 4.4, and the recommendations of the scientific literature, we propose the following scenarios for the creation of three strong protection NTZs,

incorporating elements provided by WWF Adria (Fig. 17). Three sectors are considered : **Silban Reef sector**, **Makanare Rivanj sector** and **North Veli Rat sector**.

Figure 17. Map showing the implementation scenario for No-Take Zones (hatched red polygons) surrounded by zones reserved for small-scale professional fishing (PFRA, light blue polygons) within the archipelago of Virsko More. This scenario is based on the discussion elements presented above and on potential areas identified by WWF Adria's partners (blue and light purple polygons).

5.3. Stakeholders Involvement : creating zones reserved for small-scale professional fishing

In addition to NTZs, a strategic approach to enhancing the sustainability of small-scale professional fishing within the Virsko More involves exploring successful models observed in regions such as the Bonifacio MPA in Corsica. A previous study in the Scandola Reserve (Corsica, France) demonstrated that partially protected zones designated for professional fishing (PFRAs) can provide significant benefits, sometimes comparable to those of No-Take Zones (NTZs) (Estaque et al., 2023) if fishing practices are regulated and adapted for more sustainability. Within Virsko More, PFRAs should be considered as a complementary management tool alongside NTZs to optimize both

conservation and sustainable fisheries outcomes, thus contributing to the economic well-being of local communities while minimizing the impact on the broader marine biodiversity (Fig. 17). Additionally to their benefits previously explained, such zones reserved for professional fishermen as well allow them to be considered in the decision-making process, encourage them to take part into the management and to increase the conservation effort by supporting the NTZs.

We summarized (Fig. 17) what could be a desirable new spatial planning using this approach, but the thoughtful delineation of these zones could be realized through a co-management approach, with concertation of the local fishing community. To optimize the benefits from NTZ spill over to the small scale fishery we recommend a ratio surface PFRA/surface NTZs between 2 to 3 approximately, and to draw perimeters in order to ensure a continuity in rocky favourable habitats connecting the two. It would be a way of drawing upon lessons learned from successful initiatives, such as in the Parc Marin de la Côte Bleue MPA (France). **Based on our scenario calculations** (Tab. 3), the implementation of No-Take Zones surrounded by zones reserved for professional fishermen (Professional Fishing Reserved Area, PFRA) would allow **fish production to increase significantly** compared to the present state: from 356 338 kg.year⁻¹ to 712 106 kg.year⁻¹ (i.e. 100% higher) for the **Silban Reef sector** (encompassing a NTZ and a PFRA), from 862 584 kg.year⁻¹ to 1 714 814 kg.year⁻¹ (i.e. 99% higher) for the **Makanare Rivanj sector** (encompassing a NTZ and a PFRA), and from 145 479 kg.year⁻¹ to 288 711 kg.year⁻¹ (i.e. 98% higher) for the **North Veli Rat sector** (encompassing a NTZ and a PFRA). This increase will be directly available through “spill-over” effect in zones specially reserved for small scale professional fishing (PFRA, Fig. 17).

Table 3. Sectors (as referred to in Fig. 17) and Total production in kg per year. Current production, new scenario’s productions and production increase (%) are presented for the total area of each different sector. The scenarios corresponds to the **potential production** increased by two exedentary productions resulting (1) from the setting up of the No-Take Zone (**NTZ**) and (2) resulting from the setting up of both the NTZ and the surrounding Professional Fishing Reserved Area (**PFRA**).

Sectors	Superficies NTZ/ PFRA (%)	Total area (NTZ+ PFRA) (ha)	Current Total Production Before Protection (NTZ + PFRA areas) (Kg/year)	Scenario 1 - Total Production After Protection with NTZ only (Kg/year)	Scenario 2 - Total Production After Protection with both NTZ + PFRA (Kg/year)	Difference Before/After Scenario 2 (Kg/year)	Global production increase rate for Scenario 2 (%)
Silban Reef	25.3%	2 350	356 338	383 639	712 106	355 767	100%
Majanare Rivanj	49.3%	12 540	862 584	1 357 483	1 714 814	852 230	99%
N. Veli Rat	19.7%	2 426	145 479	252 822	288 711	143 233	98%

5.4. Incorporating key habitats in the protection scheme

Besides catch management, exploring strategies to protect **critical habitats**, such as fish nurseries, is vital for effective conservation (Cheminée, 2012), since they play a fundamental role in the early stages and reproductive cycles of numerous Mediterranean fish species (Cheminée et al., 2021). Management measures should therefore prioritize the protection of nursery habitats to prevent their degradation or alteration, as such changes could compromise their ecological function (Cheminée et al., 2017). In coastal zones, various habitats within the infralittoral mosaic and their interfaces serve as crucial nurseries and should be safeguarded through stringent conservation measures (Cheminée et al., 2021). Consequently, in Virsko–More area, further local research is necessary to identify and safeguard these essential habitats.

More particularly, regarding nurseries, three key habitats within the 0–15 m depth range are of particular concern: (1) marine forests covering infralittoral rocky reefs (*Sargassaceae*, *Fucales*, *Phaeophyceae*, including forests of the genus *Cystoseira* sensu lato), (2) heterogeneous shallow bottoms (consisting of blocks and gravel on very shallow, gently sloping bottoms), and (3) *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. To ensure their effective preservation, protective measures for these habitats should prioritize mitigating the impact of other human activities rather than directly regulating fishing :

- For seagrass meadows, the impacts of ship anchoring should be regulated, and a mooring management system that meets anchoring requirements needs to be established.
- Heterogeneous shallow rocky bottoms, including the bottoms of bays and coves, are particularly vulnerable to coastal artificialization. To prevent the further destruction of these essential habitats and the associated juvenile fish assemblages, it is crucial to localize these nursery grounds to ensure their effective preservation.

Collaborative initiatives involving scientific communities and local stakeholders are *a sine qua non* condition in formulating and implementing effective protection measures of these key marine habitats, and would strengthen the resilience of the entire ecosystem (Cheminée et al., 2020). Over time, regular monitoring and adaptive management will be key components in ensuring success and long-term adaptability of these strategies.

5.5. Enforcing surveillance and regulation of recreational fishing along with promoting Public Awareness

Preventing illegal fishing activities and the overexploitation of fish stocks is crucial to maintaining the integrity of a reserve effect, once established. However, only effective surveillance can ensure the efficiency of an MPA (Rojo et al., 2019; Zupan et al., 2018). To achieve this, once conservation measures may be undertaken, it is essential to strengthen surveillance, particularly within potential future No–Take Zones (NTZs) and Partial Fishing Reserved Areas (PFRAs), including monitoring fishing practices both within and beyond the MPA.

Additionally, mitigating the "edge effect" is vital to prevent conservation gains within NTZs from being undermined (Ohayon et al., 2021). This can be achieved through the strategic management of fishing pressures at NTZ boundaries, as well as the implementation of quotas and minimum size limits for recreational fishing. Besides, the careful selection of gear types, with an emphasis on environmentally friendly and non-intrusive methods, further minimizes the impact on marine habitats.

Regular awareness campaigns and educational initiatives targeting both locals and tourists can help foster a culture of responsible angling within the MPA. It can be interesting also, to implement educational programs to raise awareness about the importance of marine conservation within the local community, among fishermen and other stakeholders such as tourists (Thompson, 2008; Urquhart et al., 2014).

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7. Appendix

Appendix A1 : Study sites - Identification number, site localisation and date on which the field-work was carried out.

Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	Sampling sites	Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)	Min Depth (m)	Max Depth (m)
24/09/2024	2	44,21329155	14,92064769	4	8
24/09/2024	3	44,20230667	14,92657833	3	6
24/09/2024	4	44,20292667	14,94358167	4	7
24/09/2024	5	44,19180833	14,98011833	4	8
24/09/2024	6	44,185555	14,99214	5	6
25/09/2024	7	44,17222833	15,00940167	3	6
25/09/2024	8	44,16187833	15,00275833	4	6
25/09/2024	10	44,153535	15,01307667	2	6
25/09/2024	11	44,13009833	15,039255	3	7
28/09/2024	12	44,10622333	14,956645	3	9
28/09/2024	13	44,13127333	14,923245	13	16
28/09/2024	14	44,13613833	14,95389333	2	8
28/09/2024	15	44,15338826	14,91810803	4	11
28/09/2024	16	44,15875196	14,90173228	10	14
28/09/2024	17	44,16486339	14,87638497	2	7
27/09/2024	18	44,15740456	14,84292246	1	7
27/09/2024	19	44,15390007	14,85144608	3	7
27/09/2024	20	44,16171333	14,822475	4	7
26/09/2024	21	44,20342	14,87863167	3	8
26/09/2024	22	44,21461833	14,85968333	2	8
26/09/2024	23	44,20882818	14,83458008	2	4
26/09/2024	24	44,22187357	14,83375301	3	6
01/10/2024	25	44,21393333	14,78946333	3	8

01/10/2024	26	44,22274833	14,76711167	4	7
01/10/2024	27	44,25603716	14,76989169	4	7
01/10/2024	28	44,27037443	14,71491163	8	12
28/09/2024	29	44,2339604	14,8669921	4	6
28/09/2024	30	44,24949833	14,83593333	4	8
30/09/2024	31	44,32842	14,69924833	4	7
29/09/2024	32	44,30520833	14,65533833	4	12
29/09/2024	33	44,334025	14,59146167	9	12
30/09/2024	34	44,345635	14,71982667	4	6
30/09/2024	35	44,38805253	14,67835953	3	10
30/09/2024	36	44,40658422	14,753298168	4	10
30/09/2024	37	44,43241687	14,73116601	2	5
30/09/2024	39	44,37204167	14,86228333	3	5
30/09/2024	38	44,40868167	14,81537833	3	5
30/09/2024	40	44,33926833	14,81120833	5	7
28/09/2024	41	44,27134167	14,798315	4	8
28/09/2024	45	44,25287833	14,82986	3	7
29/09/2024	46	44,31682667	14,62913833	8	11
01/10/2024	47	44,12378787	14,8727963	7	13
01/10/2024	48	44,13931833	14,83634667	6	13
01/10/2024	49	44,13391333	14,85196833	7	14
01/10/2024	50	44,25203833	14,74474667	3	6

Appendix A2 : List of observed species, classified by family. English common names are given for each species. Species commonly targeted by fishing are highlighted in gray.

Family	Species Sampled	Common name
Apogonidae	<i>Apogon imberbis</i>	Cardinal fish
Atherinidae	<i>Atherina sp.</i>	Silversides fishes
Carangidae	<i>Seriola dumerili</i>	Greater amberjack
Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus marginatus</i> <i>Epinephelus costae</i>	Dusky grouper Golden grouper
Labridae	<i>Coris julis</i> <i>Thalassoma pavo</i> <i>Labrus merula</i> <i>Symphodus ocellatus</i> <i>Symphodus cinereus</i> <i>Symphodus mediterraneus</i> <i>Symphodus tinca</i> <i>Symphodus roissali</i> <i>Symphodus doderleini</i> <i>Symphodus rostratus</i> <i>Centrolabrus melanocercus</i>	Mediterranean rainbow wrasse Ornate wrasse Brown wrasse Ocellated wrasse Grey wrasse Axillary wrasse East Atlantic peacock wrasse Five-spotted wrasse NA Sublet Black-tailed wrasse
Mugilidae	<i>Mugil sp.</i> <i>Chelon labrosus</i>	Mullet Thicklip grey mullet
Mullidae	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	Surmullet
Muraenidae	<i>Muraena helena</i>	Mediterranean moray
Sciaenidae	<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	Brown meagre
Scorpaenidae	<i>Scorpaena notata</i> <i>Scorpaena porcus</i>	Small red scorpionfish Black scorpionfish
Serranidae	<i>Serranus scriba</i> <i>Serranus hepatus</i>	Painted comber Brown comber
Sparidae	<i>Dentex dentex</i> <i>Sparus aurata</i> <i>Diplodus annularis</i> <i>Diplodus vulgaris</i> <i>Diplodus puntazzo</i> <i>Diplodus sargus</i> <i>Spondyliosoma cantharus</i> <i>Oblada melanura</i> <i>Sarpa salpa</i> <i>Siganus sp.</i> <i>Boops boops</i> <i>Spicara spp.</i> <i>Pagellus erythrinus</i> <i>Pagrus pagrus</i>	Common dentex Gilthead seabream Annular seabream Common two-banded seabream Sharpsnout seabream White seabream Black seabream Saddled seabream Salema Rabbitfish Bogue Picarel Common pandora Red Porgy
Sphyraenidae	<i>Sphyraena viridensis</i>	Yellowmouth barracuda

Pomacentridae	<i>Chromis chromis</i>	Damselfish
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Appendix A3 : List of Mediterranean species most commonly targeted by small scale fisheries, classified by family. English common names are given for each species.

Family	Species Sampled	Common name
Labridae	<i>Coris julis</i> <i>Labrus merula</i> <i>Labrus viridis</i>	Mediterranean rainbow wrasse Brown wrasse Green wrasse
Mugilidae	<i>Mugil</i> sp.	Mullet
Mullidae	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	Surmullet
Serranidae	<i>Serranus scriba</i>	Painted comber
Sparidae	<i>Dentex dentex</i> <i>Diplodus annularis</i> <i>Diplodus vulgaris</i> <i>Diplodus puntazzo</i> <i>Diplodus sargus</i> <i>Oblada melanura</i> <i>Pagellus erythrinus</i> <i>Pagrus pagrus</i> <i>Sarpa salpa</i> <i>Sparus aurata</i>	Common dentex Annular seabream Common two-banded seabream Sharpsnout seabream White seabream Saddled seabream Common pandora Red porgy Salema Gilt-head bream